

ANTHROPOMETRIC AND CLINICAL-DENTAL CONDITION OF THE MAXILLARY SYSTEM AND ORAL ORGANS IN PATIENTS WITH CEREBRAL PALSY

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Abstract

Background. There is a growth of patients with infantile cerebral palsy (ICP), on this basis the structure and frequency of dental pathologies in patients with ICP are estimated, taking into account morphometric parameters of the face (MP/L) and social factors of their families, as well as the importance of the age group that is a contingent of high risk of developing pathologies of the dental system (DS).

Aim. To study the mechanisms of formation of pathological processes of maxillofacial organs in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy by assessing their clinical, dental and morphometric conditions.

Material and methods. Comprehensive anthropometric, dental, laboratory and sociological studies were conducted in 299 children and adolescents from 6 to 18 years old, including 143 with CP (the main group - MG) and 156 somatically healthy (the control group - CG) in need of dental care. The results of the study were evaluated by age groups; 30.8% aged 6-9 years (MG-1); 27.3% - 10-13 years (MG-2); 42.0% - 14-18 years (MG-3); with CG - 37.2% (CG-1); 39.1% (CG-2) and 23.7% (CG-3), as well as by gender.

Results. It was found that patients with MG demonstrated poor hygiene of the oral cavity (OC) (OHI-S) within 3.0 ± 0.94 ; Plaque Index - 3.0 ± 0.84 , while it was noted that the number of incised teeth is less, and affected teeth with caries are more in patients with MG compared to CG. When comparing the parameters of the head circumference diameter, the longitudinal diameter of the head, the transverse size of the head, the vertical or height diameter of the head, the transverse size of the forehead, the zygomatic and mandibular diameter in patients with CP, the growth rate is markedly different from the norm.

Conclusion. Especially in MG-2, the proportions of the parts of the face do not correspond to the number of Fibonacci, MP/ F, with CP they are a contingent of high risk for deformation of the organs of the OC and bones of the DS.

Keywords: dentistry, caries, anomaly and deformation of teeth, psychoneurological pathology.

Relevance. According to statistics presented in the literature, "... 63% of children found that problems with their appearance negatively affect their childhood, and 37% - on their social life" [1]. According to other authors, "... the acceleration of the growth of the trunk, lower jaw (n/ h), as well as its protrusion forward is observed at the age of 11, 14, 15 years, it is established that the normalization of the overall growth of the body is manifested at the age of 7, 12-13 years, the same increase is observed in the sagittal diameter of the head" [2]. In chronic diseases, including pathology of the respiratory system, the central nervous system, a significant increase in the number of bone growth disorders of the dentoalveolar system was found [3-5]. To date, despite the development of perinatal diagnostics, the level of cerebral palsy (cerebral palsy) does not decrease, therefore, isolated and combined pathologies are often found among children and adolescents with cerebral palsy [6-8].

In recent years, statistics claim that in Uzbekistan, the spastic form of cerebral palsy (cerebral palsy) is the most common, and accounts for 80% of all cases of this

disease. Up to 800 new cases are registered annually, and today the total number of patients under 18 with cerebral palsy reaches about 40,000 patients, and accompaniment of a number of dental diseases with cerebral palsy is also noted [9-12]. Taking into account all of the above, the study of the structure, frequency of occurrence and mechanisms of formation of the pathology of DJS in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy is an urgent problem and it is necessary to develop diagnostic methods and an alternative standard of dental care for such patients.

The aim of the study is to study the mechanisms of formation of pathological processes of maxillofacial organs in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, by assessing their clinical, dental and morphometric condition.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Comprehensive anthropometric, dental and clinical laboratory studies were carried out in 299 children and adolescents; 143 of them were examined patients with cerebral palsy + mental retardation (MR) - the main group (MG); 156 somatically healthy

children and adolescents in need of dental care were selected as a control group (CG). The anthropometric parameters of the head, face, DJS, bone and dental age, as well as the clinical and dental condition of both sexes aged 6 to 18 years were evaluated, of which 44 (30.76%) aged 6-9 years (MG-1), 39 (27.27%) from

10-13 years (MG-2) and 60 (41.9%) aged 14-18 years (MG-3), with the same age division in CG - 58 (37.17%, CG-1); 61 (39.1%, CG-2) and 37 (23.7%, CG-3). Division by sex (Table No. 1) taking into account the age-related anatomical and physiological features of the stomatognathic system of the examined.

Table No. 1.

According to the age group of the examined children, n=299

Age, years	Boys		Girls		Total
	CG	MG	CG	MG	
6-9 years old	31/36,5%	28/33,8%	27/38%	16/26,7%	102/34,1%
10-13 years old	33/38,9%	25/30,1%	28/39,4%	14/23,3%	100/33,4%
14-18 years old	21/24,8%	30/36,1%	16/22,5%	30/50%	97/32,4%
Total	85/100%	83/100%	71/100%	60/100%	299/100%
From the total . research	85/28,4%	83/27,7%	71/23,8%	60/20%	299/100%

Note: MG - the main group; CG - the control group; cerebral palsy - cerebral palsy

Clinical and anthropometric characteristics of the head were evaluated by 5 indicators: head circumference (H/C), longitudinal diameter of the head (LD/H), transverse size of the head (TS /H) vertical or high-altitude diameter of the head (VD/H), transverse size of the forehead (TS/FH), for these purposes, a tasometer was used. To determine the size of the base of the head (skull), the length of the base of the head and the width of the base of the head were measured. The morphometry of the face in children was studied using a special compass and measuring tape: zygomatic and mandibular diameters (ZD/F and M), morphological height of the face (MH/F); the physiognomic height of the face (PH/F) was measured with a pelvis meter; the angle n/h with a goniometer with the mouth open. To determine the bone age of a child with cerebral palsy, the obtained R-th data were compared with the standards of bone maturation according to special R-th tables, for this purpose, according to the method of M.A. Zhukovsky et al., an R-th study of the wrist joints and the left hand of children in both study groups was performed [13].

Also carried out: basic methods of examination - collection of anamnesis, complaints, comprehensive examination of the maxillofacial area (CHLO); additional methods of examination - index assessment - CPU, CPU + cp, ICDAS II, PEC, PlaqueIndex PLI, OHI-S by Green-Vermilion (1964), PMA (Parma, 1960), PBI (Muhleman, 1975), TER, Saliva-CheckMutans express test (GC), studies of the level of cariesogenicity of dental deposits, transilluminative method for the diagnosis of carious defects and

intraoral radiography. The received materials were processed using parametric t-Student criterion or nonparametric U-criterion using Excel MS Office 2013 software.

RESULTS DISCUSSION

The analysis of the results obtained by morphometric parameters of the face (MP/F) PH/F in three age groups of boys with cerebral palsy averages 15.0 ± 0.07 cm (0.6% growth rate), and in girls on average 15.0 cm (0.4% growth rate); in girls (MG-3) with cerebral palsy indicators PH/F decreased by 0.2 units after 10-13 years, the MV/L index also decreased in the group of boys of the same age, and PH/F in boys with cerebral palsy aged 14-18 years remained unchanged – 15.2 ± 0.08 cm. At the same time, the data obtained in CG showed that the PH/F in KG-1 and KG-3 boys ranged on average 17.7 ± 0.10 cm (growth rate of 2.4%), and in girls on average 17.8 ± 0.12 cm (growth rate of 4.2%). According to the analysis of the results (Table No. 2), studies have shown that MH/F and PH/F in children with cerebral palsy are smaller in size than in healthy children. The growth rates of MH/F in healthy children are almost the same at regular intervals, whereas in children with cerebral palsy, they change abruptly or remain unchanged. Healthy male children have lower growth rates than those with cerebral palsy. It was found that the ratio of the upper, middle and lower parts of the face in girls of all groups is closer to the "golden ratio principle", compared with boys. In children with cerebral palsy, especially in boys, the ratio of the parts of the face does not correspond to the Fibonacci number.

Table No.2

Morphometric parameters of the face of children and adolescents in accordance with their "golden proportion principle".

Age and gender Couples.faces (cm)		6-9 y.o		10-13 y.o		14-18 y.o	
		Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
PH/F	CG	17,02±0,14	17,5±0,14*	17,8±0,20	17,8±0,02*	18,0±0,20	18,2±0,04*
	MG	14,8±0,14	14,8±0,04*	15,2±0,03	15,2±0,08*	15,2±0,08	15,0±0,08*
MH/F	MG	11,8±0,10	11,8±0,08	11,9±0,02	12,3±0,08	12,4±0,02	12,3±0,01
	CG	10,6±0,08	10,8±0,04*	11,2±0,08	11,0±0,02*	11,0±0,02	11,0±0,8*
HIP/F	CG	6,0±0,04	6,2±0,06	6,4±0,08	6,6±0,08	6,6±0,06	6,9±0,04
	MG	5,0±0,01	5,2±0,02	5,1±0,03	5,3±0,01	5,2±0,06	5,2±0,04
HMP/F	CG	5,8±0,05	5,9±0,02*	5,8±0,01	5,9±0,01*	6,2±0,04	6,4±0,04*
	MG	4,8,0±0,02	5,0±0,01*	4,9±0,08	5,2±0,04*	5,0±0,08	5,1±0,08*
HNP/F	CG	5,8±0,04	6,0±0,02*	5,9±0,01	6,0±0,01*	6,2±0,02	6,0±0,01*
	MG	5,0±0,12	5,2±0,08	5,1±0,04	5,2±0,04	5,1±0,8	5,2±0,06
Fibonacci Numbers	CG	1:1,60	1:1,54	1:1,61	1:1,44	1:1,68	1:1,80
	MG	1:1,405	1:1,608	1:1,400	1:1,606	1:1,355	1:1,280

Note: MG- the main group; CG – the control group; MP/H-morphometric parameters of the face; cerebral palsy-cerebral palsy; head circumference (H/C); longitudinal diameter of the head (LD/H); transverse size of the head (TS/H); vertical or height diameter of the head (VD/H); transverse forehead size (TS/FH); zygomatic and mandibular diameter (Z/D and M/D); morphological height of the face (MH/F); physiognomic height of the face (PH/F); height in/ part of the face (HIP/F); height of the middle/part of the face (HMP/F); height of the n/part of the face (HNP/F); * is a confidence indicator ($P < 0.05$) compared to the previous age.

According to the results of determining the bone age of the child, the obtained R-we compared with the norms of bone maturation according to special R-tables, it was found that in healthy male children at 6-10 years old, ossification nuclei appeared in the epiphysis of the ulna, from the age of 10 – in the awl-shaped process of the epiphysis of the ulna, and at 14 years - ossification nuclei were found in the pea-shaped bones. It was also found that in boys with cerebral palsy at the age of 6-9, ossification nuclei are visible only in the cephalic and hook-shaped bones of the wrist, and at the age of 10, ossification nuclei appeared in the epiphyses of the wrist, from the age of 14 – in the awl-shaped process of the epiphysis of the ulna. At the same time, in

girls with cerebral palsy, only the ossification nuclei in the cephalic and hook-shaped bones of the wrist are visible, and the ossification nuclei in the triangular bones of the left wrist are determined at the beginning of the 6th year of life.

The results obtained in determining the OHI-S, PLI indices and indicators for caries of temporary and permanent teeth in the studied patients are shown in Table No. 3. As can be seen from the results of patients with OH, the values of OHI-S were higher than 3.0 ± 0.98 units, in CG up to a maximum of 1.64 ± 0.44 units, which indicates poor hygiene of PR ($p < 0.0001$) in cerebral palsy compared with CG.

Table №3.

Indicators of the OHI-S index, PLI and indicators of pathology with caries in the examined groups. (M ± in %).

Groups and subgroups	Average values of OHI-S	Average PLI values (conventional unit)	Temporary teeth		Permanent teeth	
			abs.	rel. %	abs.	rel. %
MG (n = 143)	3,0±0,98	3,0±0,84	68	66,38	104	68,08
MG-1(n=44)	2,4±0,08	2,98±0,88	-	-	22	36,06
MG -2(n=39)	2,9±0,02	2,98±0,84	68	68,44	44	46,08
MG -3(n=60)	3,0±0,01	2,66±0,96	69	59,08	50	76,03
CG (n = 156)	1,64±0,44	1,88±0,98	88	86,24	90	86,24
CG -1(n=58)	1,04±0,24	1,18± 0,45	-	-	44	49,84
CG -2 (n=61)	1,04±0,24	1,18± 0,45	44	78,86	74	69,24
CG -3 (n=37)	1,04±0,24	1,18± 0,45	56	80,44	84	76,56

Note: CG - control group; MG-main group; cerebral palsy - cerebral palsy;

According to the results of a quantitative assessment of plaque, in the cervical region – Plaque Index PLI in MG - 3.0 ± 0.84 , and in CG - 1.64 ± 0.44 units, in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy, unsatisfactory hygiene was revealed. At the same time, it is noted that the number of erupted teeth is less among those examined in the MG, in comparison with CG. Also, the prevalence of caries of temporary teeth in

children and adolescents of MG was, on average, 98.88%, while among children of MG-2 in 100% of the examined there is a carious lesion of permanent and milk teeth. In CG, the prevalence of caries was 89.85%, while in CG-2, the lesion was 93.54%. Also, among the examined children and adolescents, the following were noted: hypoplasia in 45 (31.46%) children; violation of the terms of dentation - in 68 (47.55%); primary adentia

- in 78 (54.54%); anomalies of the completeness of teeth - in 90 (62.93%); endemic dental fluorosis - in 9 (6.29%); erasure of hard tissues of teeth - in 16 (10.25%); dental injuries - in 48 (30.76%); enamel necrosis - in 11 (7.69%); enamel erosion - in 28 (17.94%) patients; in the examined patients CG only in 16 (10.25%); -19 (12.17%); -42(28,84%); -21 (13,46%); -2 (1,28%); -12 (7,69%); -2 (1,28%); 9 (5,7 %); - 14 (8,9%) patients, respectively, of these pathologies.

In children and adolescents, MG is noted in 97.9% of cases, signs of periodontal inflammation, in CG - 60.89%, while periodontal pathology in patients with MG was characterized by the presence of generalized forms of varying severity -94.4%. The results of comparing the level of indicators of the OHI-S, PMA and PBI indices confirm the association of conditions for the development of periodontal diseases in both groups (Table No. 4).

Table №4.

Index assessment of periodontal and the rate of unstimulated secretion of oral fluid condition in children and adolescents of both study groups (%).

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	Сред-й по ОГ	MG-1	MG -2	MG -3	Average CG	CG-1	CG -2	CG -3
NSS, ml/min	0,27± 0,03*	0,24± 0,04	0,22± 0,08	0,33± 0,02	0,40± 0,07	0,36± 0,1	0,40± 0,04	0,43± 0,09
OHI-S, Average values OHI-S	2,8± 0,3*	2,6± 0,5	3,0± 0,1	2,8± 0,5	1,4± 0,40	1,5± 0,22	1,02± 0,01	1,3± 0,33
PMA, %	44,4± 8,4*	41,3± 5,1	48,4± 8,3	45,2± 3,4	32,4± 5,42	28,2± 5,8	26,0± 6,2	39,5± 6,08
PBI, scores	4,6± 1,2*	3,4± 1,9	5,0± 1,4	4,02± 1,	1,1± 0,1	1,08± 1	1,5± 1,1	1,2± 1
The severity of caries %	98,9± 2,04*	94,2± 1,6	100± 0,2	99,2± 2,0	89,8± 2,1	86,2± 1,2	93,5± 2	87,4± 2,
The intensity of caries of the CPD, a/v.	8,8± 0,1*	4,9± 0,8	9,9± 0,1	8,9± 0,1	4,5± 0,6	3,4± 0,8	6,04± 0,4	4,01± 0,3

Note: CG is the control group, MG is the main group; * – p <0.05 compared to the average values of the CG group; NSS is not stimulated saliva of the oral cavity.

As can be seen from Table No. 4, the indicator of the level of NSS in patients of all ages was lower than in CG by up to 1.6 times. The results demonstrate the dependence of the OHI-S and PMA index on the level of NSS products: the higher the NSS index, the lower the indicators of the OHI-S and PMA indices and the better the hygienic condition of the OC. In our opinion, according to the results of the NSS indicators, it can be qualified as a mild xerostomia, also, in patients with MG, salivation is aggravated by a decrease in the NSS

index, which can disrupt the homeostasis of the OC as a whole and is the most important risk factor for the development of pathological processes in OC.

The IgG level was 1.5 times higher relative to the comparison group, IgE was 5 times higher. The revealed fact of changes in the indicators of class E antibodies indicates that pathological changes are observed in the MG not only from the side of DJS or cerebral palsy, but also from the side of the detoxification system (Table No. 5).

Table No.5.

Indicators of systemic and local immunity in children and adolescents examined by the group.

Indicator	Clinical group (M ± σ)							
	AverageMG	MG-1	MG-2	MG-3	Average CG	CG -1	CG -2	CG -3
IgA, g/l	0,54± 0,22*	0,45± 0,1	0,49± 0,1	0,78± 0,1	1,9± 0,7	1,08± 0,4	1,4± 0,23	2,5± 0,5
IgG g/l	15,9± 2,08*	12,6± 1	17,5± 1	15,02± 0,5	10,21± 0,2	10,5± 0,3	9,3± 0,6	11± 0,1
IgE g/l	3,5± 0,5*	2,5± 3,1	5,04± 4,8	4,3± 2,3	0,44± 0,03	0,5± 0,01	0,34± 0,1	0,4± 0,1
IgM g/l	0,7± 0,08*	0,44± 0,9	0,62± 1	0,8± 0,9	1,7± 0,44	1,9± 0,49	1,7± 0,9	1,4± 0,9
Lysozyme, mcg/l	0,34± 0,08*	0,4± 0,06*	0,24± 0,1*	0,71± 0,9*	4,4± 0,45	4,6± 0,85	4,04± 0,7	4,5± 0,9
Lactoferrin, mcg/ml	0,63± 0,02*	0,75± 0,08*	0,42± 0,04*	0,65± 0,06*	1,9± 0,44	2,5± 0,8	1,24± 0,7	2,08± 0,1
sIg A, mg/l	86,3± 6,8*	99,8± 6,02*	77,4± 4,3*	84,5± 5,3*	27,03± 7,5	244,08± 9,7	226,03± 9,5	300,03± 4,4

Note: KG- the control group, OG-the main group; * – p <0.05 compared to the average values of the KG group; NSRH- unstimulated saliva of the oral cavity.

According to the analysis of the results obtained, a decrease in the content of lysozyme in the main groups was noted by 8-9 times, lactoferrin 2-2.5 times compared with CG, and it can be assumed that in the pathology of cerebral palsy there are greater deviations from the norm than in the examined children of CG.

In the process of morphofunctional study of the features of the lips and lips, pathological changes in individual and combined form in MG were 2.9 times more common than in patients with CG: the structure of pathology of the lips and lips looked as follows; in patients with MG – exfoliative cheilitis in 64 (44.75%) patients; cheilitis with lip licking - in 39 (27.27%); angular cheilitis - in 41 (28.67%); median lip fissure - in 29 (20.27%); infectious lesions of the lips of herpes labialis - in 19 (13.28%); chronic recurrent aphthae - in 19 (13.28%); traumatic lesions of the OC - in 51 (35.66%); patients with CG had such pathologies -17 (10.89%); -15 (9.61%); -19 (12.17%); -3 (1.92%); -15 (9.61%); -14 (8.97%); -5 (3.20%) accordingly. According to the results obtained, it can be seen that the frequency of occurrence of bruxism in patients with MG is 91.60% (44 b.), and NSS drouling was most often detected in MG-2 in 14 (35.89%), however, on average, the frequency of manifestations of these functional disorders in the average MG is 52.7% and 75.4%, respectively, while while these disorders were not detected among patients with CG.

According to the results of the NSS assessment in the examined children and adolescents in the MG, parents and children themselves complained of aesthetic disorders of the face (100%), including those related to the location of cutting teeth and the appearance of the lip. Parents have noticed that in children and adolescents with the existing DJS– 108 (76%) - there is a rapid increase in physical activity after classes. There is a violation of lip adhesion – in 48 (33.56%), a violation of the accuracy of pronunciation of speech sounds – in 58 (40.55%).

CONCLUSION.

Thus, the results of the study indicate that in girls with cerebral palsy aged 10-13 years, the indicators of the physiognomic height of the face were 0.2 units below the norm, in the group of boys of the same age, the MH/F indicators were low, and the PH/F indicators in boys aged 14-18 years remained unchanged, while when these indicators in CG had a growth rate of 4.2% and 2.4%, respectively, in boys and girls.

The results of determining the bone age of the child, according to special R-studies, revealed that in boys with cerebral palsy aged 6-9 years, ossification nuclei are visible only in the cephalic and hook-shaped bones of the wrist, and ossification nuclei in the epiphyses of the wrist appear after 10 years, in the awl-shaped process of the epiphysis of the ulna - from 14 years, which is evidence of tardiness of bone age of the maxillofacial region in children with spastic muscle lesions.

According to the results of a quantitative assessment of plaque in the cervical region – Plaque Index PLI, it was noted that diseases such as hypoplasia, primary adentia, anomaly of completeness of teeth, en-

demic fluorosis of teeth, dental trauma, necrosis or erosion of enamel in children with cerebral palsy are detected in 31.46% - 62.93% of cases when both examined patients have these pathologies diagnosed only in 1.28 - 28.84%, respectively.

The results of the analysis of class E antibodies (Ig G and Ig E levels) in children showed that they were 1.5 and 5 times higher relative to the comparison group, which indicated the presence of pathological changes on the part of the detoxification system.

In general, the conducted studies claim that children and adolescents with cerebral palsy are a high-risk contingent, due to improper bone formation, pathology of the PR organs, carious and non-carious lesions of the hard tissues of the teeth, periodontal tissue pathologies and diseases of the OC.

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